

**«COMPUTER-RELATED NEOLOGISMS AND THEIR
TRANSLATION INTO RUSSIAN»****Khojimatova Nigora**

lecturer at the department of pedagogy and languages

Andijan branch of Turon University

E-mail: nigoraxon6792@mail.com

Tel: (91) 495 22 11

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20526803>**ARTICLE INFO**Received: 26th May 2026Accepted: 28th May 2026Online: 30th May 2026**KEYWORDS**

the Internet, communication, sociality, a person, slang, neologisms, the virtual worldview, word formation, phonetics, graphology, the lexicological level and phraseology

ABSTRACT

The article examines the problems and specific features of Internet communication. It highlights the significant influence of informational components on society and the individual. As a result, information as a value of a new type of society is defined not only, and not so much, by its mass character or accessibility, or by its economic or political potential, but rather by its capacity for personalization, which provides its possessor with new dimensions of self-identification. The transformation of linguistic personality, accompanied by the formation of a virtual worldview, including a linguistic one, reflects life within the internet space with its specific characteristics.

Introduction. Despite the numerous articles and monographs published in recent decades addressing the problems of defining the concept of a “neologism” and its main characteristics, contemporary linguistics still lacks a unified approach to understanding the essence of newly emerging words. The term “neologism” first appeared in the French language, from which it was borrowed by other languages with the meaning of “the use or habit of using new words, innovations in language, as well as a new word or expression” [Rubleva, 2004: 117]. Traditionally, in scholarly works on linguistics and philology, the term “neologism” is used to denote new words in the various languages of the peoples of the world. A characteristic feature of neologisms that distinguishes them from lexical units belonging to the core vocabulary is their “special connection with time, a connection that is recorded by collective consciousness” [Pasechnaya, Popova, 2005: 168].

Main Part. The most important aspect determining the essence of a new word is the temporal factor (the time of its appearance) and the closely related factor of novelty, which manifests itself in the perception of a particular word as unusual, a perception shared by all speakers of a given language. The moment of a word’s appearance and disappearance in a language can be established more or less objectively. However, the duration for which lexical units retain the status of a “new word” remains one of the unresolved and therefore relevant problems of modern linguistics. In total, approximately 100 articles with an overall volume of 500,000 printed characters were analyzed. The number of neologisms identified in them amounted to 213 units. In the material analyzed by us, 104 neologisms formed by this method were identified, accounting for 48.8% of the total number of neologisms. Moreover, when

speaking of compounding, we refer not only to the combination of stems to form a new word, but also to the formation of multi-component lexical units such as *virtual keyboard*: ADC provides its customers with *always-on* broadband Internet services with no traffic limitations and offers a wide range of symmetric and asymmetric connectivity options.

The manufacturer's agent shall be in a position to attest that the *thermal management* system of the battery is neither disabled nor reduced. None of this is true in cyberspace where a weapon can consist of a few lines of code that can be invented (or purchased on the so-called *dark web*) by any number of state or non-state actors. "Zero-Emission" industrial complexes and the initiation of the "*Ecotown Pilot Project*" have also been implemented. Blogcamp Central and Eastern Europe 2008 is a yearly international "barcamp style" conference on new media – blogs, social networks, web 2.0, podcasting, online video, *citizen journalism*, etc., as well as on start-ups and venture investments.

BusinessCards MX was tested by SOFTPEDIA service. It received a certificate ensuring that it is 100% free of viruses, *spyware*, and adware. Any song can become an *earworm*, but his research has shown that some are better suited than others.

The second most frequent method of neologism formation in the field of computer technology is blending (word fusion), which at the present stage of the development of the English language is acquiring increasing importance as a word-formation device. In the material under study, 47 neologisms formed through blending were identified, accounting for 22% of the total number. The only logical explanation for this lies in the principle of linguistic economy. Moreover, many blends contain an element of language play, which, on the one hand, ensures their vitality within the language and, on the other hand, increases the popularity of the blending process itself: The Net has become a powerful way to sell to youth, whether concerned parents like it or not. For most Gen Y kids – those born in North America after 1979 (about 60 million at last count) – technology is second nature. It's as if they come into this world with a game controller in one hand and a mouse in the other. They're referred to as generation wired, cyber tots, digital kids and *screenagers*, but what they really are is business. Big business. The message said sixth graders at a Los Angeles school were investigating "where, and how fast, e-mail can travel in a period of six weeks." It asked the recipients to send a message to a mailbox at yahoo.com with their city, state and country, and then forward the students' message to everyone on the recipients' mailing lists. . . . Barbara Mikkelson says teachers setting up Internet projects underestimate the pleasure people get out of doing something that feels like a public service yet requires no more than a few keystrokes. Рассмотрим более подробно примеры неологизмов, которые переводятся при помощи транскрипции и транслитерации:

alpha-Blending – альфа-блендинг (транслитерация);

audiophile – Аудиофил (транскрипция + транслитерация);

bashtag – Баштэг (транскрипция + транслитерация);

blook – блук (транскрипция);

Brexit – Брекзит (транскрипция);

click bait – кликбэйт (транскрипция);

crowdsourcing – краудсорсинг (транскрипция + транслитерация);

darknet – даркнет (транскрипция + транслитерация);

dollarization – долларизация (транслитерация);
egosurfer – эгосёрфер (транскрипция + транслитерация);
flashmob – флешмоб (транскрипция);
geobragging – геобрагинг (транслитерация);
hashtag – хэштег (транскрипция);
hater – хэйтер (транскрипция + транслитерация);
infomania – инфомания (транслитерация);
noob – нуб (транскрипция);
ping – пинг (транслитерация);
spam – спам (транслитерация);
troll – троллить (транслитерация);
vlog – влог (транскрипция = транслитерация);
wi-fi – вай фай (транскрипция).

However, this translation method can hardly be considered effective for such neologisms as blends, since Russian-speaking readers are unlikely to understand words such as *blook* (blog + book = blook — a book written by a blogger) or *vlog* (video + blog = vlog — a video blog). The techniques of transcription and transliteration were applied in the translation of 20 items from the total number of translation techniques employed. Let us provide examples of descriptive translation used in the material analyzed in our study:

always-on – имеющий постоянный доступ к электронным услугам;
bling – дорогие вещи выставляемые на показ в социальных сетях;
clothesaholic – человек, одержимый одеждой;
completionist – игрок стремящийся получить все достижения в видео игре;
crunk – очень активный человек успевающий отвечать всем в общем чате, часто раздражительно активный;
decicorn – стартап собравший более 10 миллиардов долларов;
deerweb – дебри интернета;
dilatary – тратить время в пустую уткнувшись в телефон;
dox – публикация персональной информации без согласия правообладателя;
dronevertising – необычные способы размещения рекламы;
esports – турнир по киберспорту;
farecasting – сайт-агрегатор авиа и жд билетов;
feature creature – любитель дополнительных функций, свойств компьютеров или программ;
geocache – игра с использованием GPS основанная на поиске спрятанных подсказок и вещей;
haptics – инструмент взаимодействия слепых людей с компьютером;
locavore – человек питающийся в основном пищей местного производства;
lookupable – заслуживающее внимания;
mic drop – добиться превосходства и закончить дискуссию;

pageview – регулярное посещение одной и той же страницы в интернете;

permadeath – смерть игрового персонажа;

Conclusion. The expansion of the vocabulary of modern English occurs almost entirely through internal linguistic resources, while foreign borrowings play only a minimal role. The majority of new words enter the English language through productive word-formation processes such as compounding, blending, affixation, abbreviation, conversion, reduplication, and, more rarely, coinage. A neologism should be regarded as a normal linguistic phenomenon, and the absence of a word from a dictionary cannot serve as an obstacle to its translation. Moreover, it is translation practice that makes the greatest contribution to enriching the vocabulary of the target language with new words borrowed from other languages and, consequently, to expanding the entries of bilingual dictionaries.

In any case, once the meaning of a new word is known, it can be rendered using the translation methods discussed above. Thus, the process of translating neologisms from English into Russian consists of two stages:

1. Determining the meaning of the neologism (when the translator either consults the latest editions of English explanatory or encyclopedic dictionaries or infers the meaning of the new word by considering its structure and context).

2. The actual translation (rendering) into Russian by means of transcription, transliteration, calquing, or descriptive translation (either explanatory or substitutive. When the latter method is used, one may observe either complete equivalence of denotative meanings, a narrowing or broadening of the meaning of the target-language word, or partial correspondence between the meanings of the source-language and target-language lexical units).

As for the choice of a particular method for rendering neologisms, it depends on many subjective factors, such as the translator's personality, experience, intellect, ability to operate with abstract concepts, and the conditions under which the translation is performed, as well as on the style of the text (journalistic, scientific, literary, etc.), the style of the particular author, and other considerations. Above all, however, it is necessary to ensure that the equivalent chosen for the source-language neologism (English) corresponds as closely as possible to the norms and rules of the target language (Russian).

References:

1. Vinogradova, T.Yu. Specifics of Communication on the Internet // Russian and Comparative Philology: Linguocultural Aspect. – Kazan, 2004. – pp. 63–67.
2. Altynbekova, O.B. Ethnolinguistic Processes in Kazakhstan. – Almaty, 2006. – 415 p.
3. Aksenova, M.E., Petranovskaya, L.G. Avanta+. Linguistics. – Moscow: Avanta+, 2005. – 704 p.
4. Goldenkov, M.A. Beware! Hot Dog! – Moscow: CheRo, 1999. – 272 p.
5. Galperin, I.R. On the Term "Slang". – Moscow: Questions of Linguistics, 1956, No. 6.
6. Kuchnikov, T.V. Communication on the Internet. – Moscow: Alliance-Press, 2004. – 128 p.